

Modeling Water Condensation on Fruit Bulks Exposed to Temperature Fluctuations

Thanut NUANGJAMNONG^{*(a)}, Steven DURET^(a), Amel MEDJDOUB^(a),
Denis FLICK^(b), Jean MOUREH^(a), Graciela ALVAREZ^(a),

(a) Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, FRISE, 92761, Antony, France

(b) Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR SayFood, 91120, Palaiseau, France

*Corresponding author: thanut.nuangjamnong@inrae.fr

ABSTRACT

In the supply chain of fruits and vegetables, products are cooled down and stored in cold storage. However, they may be exposed to temperature fluctuations in the refrigeration system or when the cold product is submitted to the warm ambiance when the product is transported from one place to another. Water condensation can occur on the product surface. When the cold product is exposed to warm air, water condenses on the produce surface at temperatures below the dew point. Condensation on the product surface is an unfavourable condition for product quality. This promotes spore formation and the growth of microorganisms. This study aims to develop a model of heat and mass transfer in bulk fruits, including condensation. The model predicts air and product temperatures and water condensation within a container exposed to temperature fluctuations and was validated against experimental data. This model can potentially predict air and product temperature evolution and accumulation of water condensation.

Keywords: Water condensation, Temperature fluctuation, Heat transfer, Mass transfer

1 INTRODUCTION

Blueberries (*Vaccinium spp.*) are well known as superfood because of their nutrition and potent antioxidant activities in the human body (Banerjee et al., 2020). Nevertheless, blueberries are perishable (Chiabrando and Giacalone, 2011). Temperature is the main factor affecting the physiological and biochemical processes in the product. Therefore, the product should be reduced temperature after harvesting (Duan et al., 2020). However, due to the complex cold supply chain, the products are not maintained in optimal conditions throughout the supply chain (Chaomuang et al., 2022; Ndraha et al., 2018).

In the refrigeration system, condensation can occur due to temperature fluctuations. Condensation occurs when a cold product is subjected to warm and humid air so that the product's surface temperature is below the air dew point. When the product temperature rises above the air dew point, condensate on the surface can evaporate and return to the surrounding air (Linke et al., 2021). Water condensation at the product surface is unwanted because it leads to defects in the product's loss (Linke and Geyer, 2013).

Several studies on heat and mass transfer in food stacks. Laguerre and Flick (2004) compared the transient heat transfer by free convection in a packed bed of spheres using the direct CFD and porous medium approaches. Both approaches showed good accuracy in predicting temperature. Urquiola et al. (2017) proposed a numerical model using the porous media approach under natural convection to predict temperature as well as frost formation during storage of frozen sliced carrots.

This study aims to develop a model of heat and mass transfer under natural convection using a porous media approach to predict temperature and water condensation in bulk fruits exposed to temperature fluctuation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experiment set-up

Commercial-grade blueberries were used in this experiment. They were bought from supermarkets near the laboratory (Antony, France). Rotten and damaged blueberries were removed and stored in an almost cylindrical polypropylene container with a volume of 1.24 liters (internal diameter 100 mm at the bottom; 120 mm at the top; height 130 mm; wall thickness l_w 1.0 mm; thermal conductivity, k_w $0.17 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$). The blueberries were distributed into four distinct sections (A, B, C and D) within grid baskets. These baskets divided the container into central and near-wall areas on two levels, allowing the analysis of temperature and condensation within the container. The top and bottom of the container were insulated with expanded polystyrene (EPS). The temperature of the external side of the lateral container wall was measured and used as a boundary condition. A household refrigerator (CHiQ) was used, with temperature control by a thermostat set to 4°C .

2.2 Temperature and condensation measurements

The container filled with blueberries was placed in the refrigerator at 4°C for 24 hours to stabilize the temperature. Subsequently, it was taken out and exposed to room temperature (20°C) for 1 hour before being returned to the refrigerator for 5 hours. Temperature measurements were conducted using T-type thermocouples (precision $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$), which had been calibrated at five specific temperatures (-5°C , 0°C , 5°C , 15°C , and 35°C). These thermocouples were connected to a data logger (Keysight DAQ970A) linked to a computer. The product, air, and container temperatures were recorded at 1-minute intervals. Four blueberries within the container were equipped with thermocouples to measure product temperatures at the center of areas A, B, C, and D. Additionally, four thermocouples were positioned to monitor the air temperature around the product in each of these areas. We carefully placed in order to avoid that air thermocouples were in contact with any surface. External wall temperature and ambient temperature were also measured.

Fig. 1. Diagram of thermocouples position.

Water condensation was measured by weighing the condensed water on the product surface in different areas (A, B, C, and D) of the container. After the 1-hour heating phase, the container was opened, and blueberries from each area were removed and weighed separately in the order of C, D, A, and B. Absorbent paper was then used to remove the condensed water from the product surfaces. The dried blueberries were weighed again using the same balance (OHAUS EX10202, 0.01 g accuracy). The amount of condensed water was determined as the difference between the initial and final weights.

2.3 Modeling heat and mass transfer

This two-dimensional (2D) axisymmetric transient model for the bulk-stored blueberries was adapted from the heat and mass transfer model for frozen carrots developed by (Urquiola et al., 2017).

2.3.1 Assumption

1. The stack of blueberries was assumed to be a porous medium.
2. Airflow in the container was considered as laminar flow.
3. The Boussinesq approximation was employed. A linear relation between air density and air temperature, $\rho = \rho_a [1 - \beta(T_a - T_{ref})]$ was used.
4. The internal thermal resistance of blueberries was neglected, (Biot number $\ll 0.1$).
5. Internal water transfer resistance within the blueberries was disregarded.
6. Radiative heat transfer was neglected.
7. The dispersion term in the energy equation for the porous medium was also neglected.

2.3.2 Continuity and momentum equations with the Boussinesq approximation.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$\frac{\rho_a}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + \frac{\rho_a}{\varepsilon^2} (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\vec{\nabla} P + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{v} - \frac{\mu}{K} \vec{v} - \rho_a \beta (T_a - T_{ref}) \vec{g} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where ε is the porosity of blueberries stack, \vec{v} is the superficial velocity of the fluid in the porous medium (m.s^{-1}) or Darcy velocity, μ is the dynamic viscosity of air (Pa.s), K is the permeability of the porous medium (m^2) and β is the thermal coefficient of volumetric expansion (K^{-1}).

2.3.3 Energy equation

The energy equations for air, Eq. (3) and for the product, Eq. (4), are coupled through the convective heat transfer. Furthermore, the latent heat of water evaporation is accounted for in the energy equation of the product.

$$\rho_a C_{p_a} \varepsilon \frac{\partial T_a}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\vec{v} \rho_a C_{p_a} T_a) = k_a \nabla^2 T_a + h A_{spec} (T_p - T_a) \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$\rho_p C_{p_p} (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = k_{eq} \nabla^2 T_p + h A_{spec} (T_a - T_p) + \left(\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial t} \right) H_{evap} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

Where k_{eq} is the equivalent thermal conductivity of the porous medium ($\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$), A_{spec} is the specific surface area of blueberry defined as the surface area of blueberry over the total volume of a container (m^{-1}), h is the heat transfer coefficient between the internal air and the blueberries, H_{evap} is the latent heat of evaporation, C_2 and C_3 are described in section 2.3.4.

2.3.4 Water mass balance equation

The total water mass balance equation is adapted from Urquiola et al. (2017).

$$\frac{\partial (\varepsilon C_1 + C_2 + C_3)}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla C_1 = D_{eff} \nabla^2 C_1 \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

Where C_1 is the water content in the air of porous medium (kg per m^3 of air), C_2 is the water content in the condensate of porous medium (kg per m^3 of porous medium), C_3 represents the water content loss in the product at a given time (kg per m^3 of porous medium) and D_{eff} is the effective mass diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium.

The water condensation equation is shown in Eq. (6). Water condenses when the water vapor concentration in the air is higher than the saturated water vapor concentration at the product temperature while water evaporates when the water vapor concentration in the air is lower than the saturated water vapor concentration at the product temperature and if condensate is already present on product's surface.

$$\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} h_m A_{spec} (C_1 - C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 > C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ (Condensation)} \\ h_m A_{spec} (C_1 - C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 < C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ and } C_2 > 0 \text{ (Evaporation)} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

Where h_m is mass transfer coefficient ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$).

The saturated vapor concentration, $C_{sat}(T)$ is calculated from Eq. (7), assuming the air is an ideal gas.

$$C_{sat}(T) = \frac{P_{sat}(T)M}{RT} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

where $P_{sat}(T)$ is the saturated vapor pressure (Pa).

The product dehydration equation is described in Eq. (8); it occurs when the water vapor concentration in the air is lower than the water vapor concentration in the air in equilibrium with the product and if there is no water at the product surface.

$$\frac{\partial C_3}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_m} + R_{skin}} \times A_{spec} (C_1 - a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) & \text{if } (C_1 < a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ and } C_2 = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } (C_1 > a_w C_{sat}(T_p)) \text{ or } C_2 > 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

Where R_{skin} is the skin resistance of the product ($\text{s}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) and a_w is the water activity of blueberry, assumed to be one.

The Lewis analogy was applied to calculate the mass transfer coefficient as shown in Eq. (9).

$$h_m = \frac{h}{\rho_a c p_a} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

2.3.5 Initial conditions

For the simulation, the air velocity is assumed to be zero at the initial. The initial air temperature and product temperatures are obtained from measurements. The water content in air (C_1), water content in condensate (C_2), and water content loss in the product (C_3) is zero initially.

2.3.6 Boundary conditions

The no-slip condition at the wall was applied. Therefore, the velocity at the walls is zero. The container was assumed to be fully insulated at the top and bottom walls, resulting in no heat flux through these sides. Heat flux on the insulated walls was assumed to be zero. For the heat flux through the lateral walls, it was assumed to be transferred by conduction to the air or product in proportion to their volume fractions ($1-\epsilon$, ϵ) representing the wall-to-air and wall-to-product interactions, respectively. No mass transfer between the external air and the internal air within the closed container.

2.4 Parameter identification

To solve the differential equations, parameters were determined through measurements, calculations or literature.

2.4.1 Product bulk porosity

The porosity is evaluated by measuring the void volume of the porous medium using water. The porosity (ε) is 0.40.

2.4.2 Diameter and density of blueberry

A sample of 100 blueberries was measured weight using a scale (OHAUS EX10202) with a precision of 0.01 g. The volume was measured by the water displacement method and the density was calculated to be 1023 kg.m⁻³. Using the total volume (100 blueberries), the average equivalent diameter of a single blueberry was estimated to be 0.0148 m.

$$d = \left(\frac{6V_p}{100\pi}\right)^{1/3} \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

2.4.3 Specific surface

The specific surface is defined as the ratio between the total surface of a product and the total volume of the container and is calculated using Eq. (11).

$$A_{spec} = \frac{A_{total\ surface}}{V_{container}} = \frac{6(1-\varepsilon)}{d} \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

The calculated specific surface (A_{spec}) is 243 m⁻¹.

2.4.4 Product specific heat capacity

The specific heat capacity (Cp_p) of the blueberry is 3830 J.kg⁻¹.K⁻¹ obtained from ASHRAE (2022).

2.4.5 Permeability

The bulk product permeability was calculated by using the Carman–Kozeny equation (Nield and Bejan, 2013).

$$K = \frac{d^2 \varepsilon^3}{180(1 - \varepsilon)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

Where d is average diameter of blueberry. The calculated permeability is 2.16 x 10⁻⁷ m².

2.4.6 Skin resistance

The skin resistance, R_{skin} describes the resistance of water passing through the peel of a blueberry and can be calculated by Eq. (13) as reported by Becker et al. (1996).

$$R_{skin} = \frac{M}{R \cdot T_{ref} \cdot k_s} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

Where R represents the universal gas constant (8.314 J.mol⁻¹.K⁻¹), T_{ref} is the reference temperature (277.15 K), and M is the molar mass of water (18.02 x 10⁻³ kg.mol⁻¹). The skin mass transfer coefficient, k_s is 2.19 x 10⁻⁹ kg.m⁻².s⁻¹.Pa⁻¹.

2.4.7 Equivalent thermal conductivity

The equivalent thermal conductivity of bulk blueberries was experimentally determined using a one-dimensional heat conduction model in COMSOL. Blueberries were placed in an insulated box (0.153 × 0.107 × 0.093 m) closed with a steel plate at the top. Temperature was recorded using T-type thermocouples: one at the center of the blueberries and another on the steel plate. After 24 hours at 4°C, the box was heated from the top using a phase-change material (melting point 16°C) to avoid natural convection. The equivalent thermal conductivity was identified by minimizing the sum of the squared differences between measured and simulated temperatures, a value k_{eq} of 0.18 W.m⁻¹.K⁻¹ was obtained and used in the model.

2.4.8 Convective heat transfer coefficient

The Churchill correlation for natural convection for spheres was used to calculate the Nusselt number (Holman, 2010).

$$Nu = 2 + \frac{0.589Ra^{0.25}}{[1 + (\frac{0.469}{Pr})^{0.563}]^{0.444}} \quad \text{Eq. (14)}$$

Where Ra is the Rayleigh number. It can be calculated using Eq. (16).

$$Ra = GrPr = \frac{g\beta(T_p - T_\infty)d^3}{\nu^2} Pr \quad \text{Eq. (15)}$$

Where Gr is the Grashof number, Pr is the Prandtl number and T_∞ is the surrounding air temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$).

Heat transfer coefficient, h ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) is calculated from the Nusselt number.

$$Nu = \frac{h \cdot d}{k_a} \quad \text{Eq. (16)}$$

Where d is diameter of a blueberry (m) and k_a is thermal conductivity of air.

In this study, the temperature difference between product and air was observed to be between 0 and 2.2 K. The average convective heat transfer coefficient of $5.5 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$.

2.4.9 Effective mass diffusivity

For the effective mass diffusivity, the diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium account for the mass diffusivity of water vapor in air and porosity given by Eq. (18) obtained from Nield and Bejan (2013).

$$D_{eff} = D_v \varepsilon \quad \text{Eq. (17)}$$

Where ε is the porosity of porous medium and D_v is the diffusivity of water vapor in air at reference temperature ($2.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) obtained from Cengel and Ghajar (2020). For nominal value, the effective mass diffusivity was $D_{eff} = 8.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

2.5 Numerical Resolution

COMSOL Multiphysics (Version 5.6) was used to solve the set of differential equations. A mesh sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the effect of mesh resolution on simulation results. An automatic physics-controlled mesh was used, consisting of 3532 cells for the Fine mesh and 8580 cells for the Finer mesh. The tests involved simulating a container with insulation at the top and bottom, subjected to an imposed temperature profile. The results showed very small variations in air and product temperatures between the Fine and Finer meshes, with a difference in water condensation of 0.0015 g, accounting for 0.7% of the total water condensation. However, the computational time doubled when using the Finer mesh. Therefore, the Fine mesh was selected for the studies.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Validation air and product temperature evolution and water condensation in the container with insulation

Simulated and experimental air temperature and product temperature in the container with insulation at the top and bottom are shown in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b, respectively. There is a relatively good agreement between experiment and simulation. Both air and product temperature show the same behavior. The air and product temperature are almost equal. This is explained by the low thermal inertia of the air

associated with the low air velocity due to natural convection. Actually, the thermal characteristic time of the air is less than 1 second ($\tau_a = \varepsilon \cdot \rho_a \cdot C p_a / h \cdot A_{spec} = 0.4$ second). Air and product temperature mainly depend on the radial position: the further from the wall, the more the temperature variation imposed at the wall was delayed. At a given radial position, the temperature was slightly higher near the top, the difference being more pronounced in the experimental results. This temperature difference between the top and bottom positions can be explained by natural convection phenomena in the container.

Fig. 2. Comparison between experimental and simulated temperatures in the container with insulation at the top and bottom: a. air temperature, b. product temperature

During the first 60 minutes, the container (initially at 4°C) was exposed to room temperature. It was heated from the side wall and both product, and air temperatures near the wall (B and D) increased rapidly because of the large difference between air and product temperature and wall temperature. In contrast, the product and air temperatures at the center of the container (A and C) increased, as expected, slower. After 60 minutes, the container was returned to the refrigerator (4°C). As the container was cooled from the side wall, the air, and product temperature at zones B and D decreased instantly while those in the central area continued to increase for 60 minutes. This can be explained by the thermal inertia of porous media.

Regarding the results of the model, they agree with the experiment results. For example, the model describes well the initial sharp increase in areas B and D (external) as well as the delayed increase in areas A and C (centre). It is to be also noticed that the maximum temperature is well predicted in zones D and C (top) while slightly overestimated in zones A and B (bottom) as the simulation does not exhibit temperature differences between the top area and bottom area highlighted in the experiments.

Both air and product temperatures in the external areas (B and D) exhibit higher deviations than those in the internal areas (A and C). The highest deviations in air temperature are 11.0%, 16.4%, 13.1%, and 21.6% for areas A, B, C, and D, respectively. Similarly, the highest deviations in product temperature are 11.8%, 21.9%, 7.4%, and 11.6% for areas A, B, C, and D, respectively.

At the end of heating (60 minutes), the water condensation on the product surface in the container with insulation was measured. The experimental water condensation was 0.55 g. As shown in Fig. 3, the experimental results indicate that the highest percentage of water condensation (33%) occurs in area D.

In this study, a closed container was used and the air inside the container was assumed to be saturated. Due to the enclosed environment, measuring the relative humidity inside the container was challenging and was therefore not performed. Similarly, the relative humidity of the surrounding environments, including the refrigerator and the room, was not measured, as the experimental design was focused on the water condensation on the surface of blueberries within the closed container. Additionally, measuring the mass of water condensation in fruit bulks is challenging.

Fig. 3. Percentage of experimental water condensation in each area in a container with insulation.

The simulated water condensation on product surface in each area is shown in Fig. 4. Water condensation in every area increased in the first 60 minutes when the container was exposed to the warm temperature. After that, water condensation in areas A and B decreased (evaporation) while water condensation in areas C and D continually increased when the container was stored in the refrigerator.

Fig. 4. Simulated water condensation on product surface in the insulated with insulation.

3.2 Effect of ambient temperature in air and product temperature and water condensation in the container with insulation at the top and bottom

Two simulated temperature cycles were used in the study to analyze the effect of external temperature on air and product temperatures and water condensation inside a container with insulation at the top and bottom: high temperature cycle (40°C for one hour and 4°C for five hours) and low temperature cycle (10°C for one hour and 4°C for five hours).

Figs. 5 and 6 show the simulated air and product temperatures for the high temperature cycle and low temperature cycle, respectively. Significant temperature differences between the top areas (A and B) and bottom areas (C and D) can be observed in the simulated temperatures under the high temperature

cycle, with differences exceeding 3°C at 60 minutes. However, temperature differences between the top areas (A and B) and bottom areas (C and D) under the low-temperature cycle were less than 0.5°C at 60 minutes. This is because the temperature difference between the air and the product and the temperature of the external wall affects the rate of natural convection within the container.

Simulated water condensation on the product surface inside the container with insulation at the top and bottom is shown in Figs. 7a and 7b for the high temperature and low temperature cycles, respectively. Under the 40°C high temperature cycle, water condensation increased significantly, reaching 1.9 g at 60 minutes, compared to 0.6 g under the 10°C low temperature cycle. This difference is attributed to the heating of the container from the lateral wall during the high temperature cycle, which causes the temperature near the wall to rise. As a result, the relative humidity decreases, promoting dehydration of the product and evaporation of moisture into the air. Since the air temperature in the high temperature cycle is warmer than in the low temperature cycle, the air can hold more moisture. Consequently, the higher evaporation rate in the high temperature cycle leads to greater water condensation.

Fig. 5. Simulated temperatures under high temperature cycle in the container with insulation top and bottom: a. air temperature, b. product temperature

Fig. 6. Simulated temperatures under low temperature cycle in the container with insulation at top and bottom: a. air temperature, b. product temperature

Fig. 7. Simulated water condensation on product surface in the container with insulation at top and bottom: a. high temperature cycle, b. low temperature cycle.

4 Conclusion

A study was conducted to examine temperature and water condensation in a bulk fruit container subjected to simulated temperature variations. Experiments were performed using a container insulated at the top and bottom. A heat and mass transfer model for a porous medium under natural convection was developed and validated. The results demonstrate that the model accurately predicts air and product temperatures throughout the container under varying temperature conditions. The ambient temperature can impact the natural convection phenomenon and water condensation within the container. This model holds significant potential for future research involving more complex geometries.

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NOMENCLATURE

A	Surface area (m^2)	L	Height of the container (m)
A_{spec}	Specific surface of the blueberries (m^2 of product surface per m^3 of porous medium)	M	Molecular mass ($kg \cdot mol^{-1}$)
a_w	Water activity	m	Mass (kg)
Bi	Biot number	Nu	Nusselt number
C_1	Water content in the air of porous medium ($kg \cdot m^{-3}$ of air)	Pr	Prandtl number
C_2	Water content in the condensate of porous medium ($kg \cdot m^{-3}$ of porous medium)	P	Pressure (Pa)
C_3	Reduction of water content in the product of porous medium ($kg \cdot m^{-3}$ of porous medium)	R	Universal gas constant ($J \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
C_p	Specific heat at constant pressure ($J \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	R_{skin}	Skin mass transfer resistance ($s \cdot m^{-1}$)
D	Internal diameter of container (m)	r	Radial position (m)
		Sc	Schmidt number
		T	Temperature (K)
		t	Time (s)
		V	Volume, m^3

D_{eff}	Effective mass diffusivity of water vapor in the porous medium ($m^2.s^{-1}$)	v	Fluid superficial velocity ($m.s^{-1}$)
D_v	Diffusivity of water vapor in air ($m^2.s^{-1}$)	X	Mass fraction
d	Average diameter of blueberries (m)	ρ	Density ($kg.m^{-3}$)
g	Gravitation acceleration ($m.s^{-2}$)	β	Thermal expansion coefficient of air (K^{-1})
H_{evap}	Latent heat of evaporation ($J.kg^{-1}$)	ε	Porosity
h	Convective heat transfer coefficient ($W.m^{-2}.K^{-1}$)	μ	Dynamic viscosity (Pa.s)
h_m	Convective mass transfer coefficient ($m.s^{-1}$)	ν	Kinematic viscosity ($m^2.s^{-1}$)
K	Permeability (m^2)	τ	Tortuosity
k	Thermal conductivity ($W.m^{-1}.K^{-1}$)	exp.	Experiment
k_s	Skin mass transfer coefficient ($kg.m^{-2}.s^{-1}.Pa^{-1}$)	p	Products
Indices		ref	Reference
a	Air	sat	Saturated
eq.	Equivalent	sim	Simulation
		w	Wall
		∞	Surrounding air

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